

The Austrian Raids across the Danube near Klosterneuburg (3-4 July 1809)

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The current article was prompted by a chance discovery by one of the authors during archival research in the Augustinian Abbey of Klosterneuburg directly north of Vienna. Inside carton box K 219, amidst a rather eclectic collection of miscellaneous documents dating from the late Middle Ages to the early 19th century, an interesting source came to light. This was a small square envelope containing two round bullets. On the outside the following note was written in elegant *kurrent* hand:

'Two bullets which were shot on July 1809 at 11 o'clock at night by I[mperial]-R[oyal] Austrian

Jägers positioned in the Au into the room of the ble[ssed] venerable Ignatius Dauderlau on the second floor of the new building.'

Several points can be deduced from the discovery itself. Firstly, the reference to Canon Ignatz Dauderlau as 'blessed' denotes that the envelope was filed in the archive after his death on 6 May 1810. Secondly, the distance between the edge of the Klosterneuburg *Au* – [two flood islands in the Danube stream channel](#) – and the baroque (i.e. new) wing of the Abbey measured about 200 metres. This was within the effective range of well trained early 19th century riflemen.¹ In other words, the event described in the note is actually feasible. Finally, none of the major histories of the War of 1809 mention any fighting in Klosterneuburg immediately before the decisive battle of Wagram. Therefore, it appears that the envelope with the two inconspicuous bullets bears witness to a military action completely unknown before. Extraordinarily, the events of 3rd and 4th July 1809 could be reconstructed almost hour by hour from the first-hand accounts by members of the monastic community and from the

operational reports of the Austrian Army preserved in the State Archives in Vienna. In so doing, we gained valuable insight not only into the military events upstream of Vienna during the supposedly quiet time before Wagram, but also into the experiences of the Austrian civilians in areas occupied by the French and their allies. On one hand, the Augustinian canons of Klosterneuburg were compelled to accommodate and placate the garrison imposed on them by the enemy. On the other, their loyalty lay firmly with their own country whose army was still fighting across the river.

1809 was not the first time that the Abbey came into contact with the French. In autumn 1805, Klosterneuburg was occupied for two months by the *Grand Armée* following the Austrian defeat at Ulm. The Abbey and the town had to quarter and provide for the enemy troops. In the outlying parishes farther from the main road and away from the direct oversight of their officers, French soldiers took matters into their own hands by looting and abusing the local people. Less than four years later, Napoleon's army came back. On 10th of May 1809, French soldiers entered the abbey, demanding food, wine and money. As fighting continued to rage across the Danube, the Augustinian Canons had to feed the French troops quartered there as well as the allied Württembergers who were tasked with permanently garrisoning Klosterneuburg. In addition, a high war contribution was imposed. After the enemy troops finally left in November 1809, the economic consequences of their presence continued to haunt the Abbey for many years to come.²

Two bullets from the Abbey

¹ Karl Kandeldorfer, *Das k. k. oberösterreichische Feldjäger-Bataillon Nr. 3 im Kampfe mit Oesterreichs Gegnern*, (Linz: Akademische Privatdruckerei, 1882), p. 5.

² Floridus Röhrig, 'Klosterneuburg', in: Floridus Röhrig (ed.), *Die bestehenden Stifte der Augustiner Chorherren in Österreich, Südtirol und Polen*, Österreichisches Chorherrenbuch 2, (Vienna: Mayer & Comp., 1997) pp. 99–193 [here p. 142].

These events are described by three members of the Abbey: Archivist and Librarian Lorenz Maximilian Fischer (1782-1851), and Canon Gregor Hummel (1783-1869) whose *Notata vom Jahre 1809* integrates material compiled by Dean Augustin Herrmann (1757-1828). Excerpts from the latter source were published before, including the parts covering 1809. These appeared in German in 1909, 1927 and 1972.³ In 2009, a French summary of the compound narrative of Hermann and Hummel was published by Robert Ouvrard, albeit without mentioning its authors.⁴ The current Bulletin offers the first ever English translation of this important source. The information provided by the monastic authors on the daily life in the Abbey during the French occupation is particularly valuable. This was not just about the extortions of the occupiers, but also their demeanour. For instance, the enemy troops did not bother returning the cutlery and dishes, making it hard for the monks who had to continue serving them food and drink again, again and again.⁵ Although their own safety dictated that they had to do their best not to offend their occupiers, the authors made no secret as to where their sympathies lay. The Austrian troops are referred to as

‘ours’ and Hummel even speaks about ‘our *Jägers*’ when they were firing on his Abbey. Furthermore, the monastic authors do not bother concealing their delight when some misfortune fell upon the French or their Württemberger sidekicks.⁶

There is also interesting information provided on the military operations as far as these could be observed from the Monastery. In June, things were mostly quiet and Austrian and Württemberger pickets from both sides of the Danube were often heard shouting at each other. However, early next month it became clear that something was at hand. In the entry for 2nd July 1809, the Hermann/Hummel narrative notes: ‘In general, one notices from the frequent marching and, especially, from the activity in Vienna that another major offensive is being prepared’. As it turned out, this was right. A large new battle was about to be fought, but the Abbey was hit even sooner:

‘In the night of 3-4 [July], at 11 o’clock, Austrian Jägers in the Au opposite the Monastery began to fire heavily at our windows: several bullets flew into the prelatry; two came through the corridor window of the dormitory; and one into the middle room of the Deanery. Fortunately—praise

be to God – no one was hit during the shooting.’⁷

While the room of Canon Dauderlau is not mentioned, the note attached to the bullets in the archive makes it clear his quarters were hit as well. The accounts of that night’s events are confirmed by records of the Viennese War Archives. These further reveal why Austrian troops fired at one of their country’s most important monasteries.

In 1809 the only bridge over the Danube near Vienna was *Am Spitz*, not far from the modern Floridsdorf Bridge. After the fiasco four years earlier, when Marechal Murat captured it by ruse, this bridge had been burned by the Austrians as soon as the French had approached the city. On 13th May – the same day Vienna capitulated to Napoleon – his troops tried to force a crossing near the ruined bridge landing in the *Schwarzen-Lacken-Au* – at that time an island off the eastern bank of the Danube near the village of Jedlesee. Quick reaction by the 49th Line Infantry Regiment ‘Kerpen’, supported by units of the Lower Austrian Landwehr, repulsed the French. The Austrians were less successful downstream where the French secured Lobau Island several days later. Napoleon’s attempt to break out into the east bank was soundly defeated at the

³ Berthold Otto Černik, ‘Tagebücher des Stiftes Klosterneuburg über die Invasionen der Franzosen in Österreich in den Jahren 1805 und 1809’, *Jahrbuch des Stiftes Klosterneuburg* 2 (1909), pp. 155-230; Vinzenz Oskar Ludwig and Claire E. Stransky, *Napoleon in Oesterreich. Szenen und Karikaturen aus Klosterneuburgs Franzosenzeit*, Kleine historische Monographien, Dritte Reihe: Historische Schriftdenkmäler 1, (Vienna: Reinhold 1927); The latter was reprinted verbatim as ‘Aus der Franzosenzeit 28. Fortsetzung: Das Stift Klosterneuburg im Jahr 1809’, *Wagramer Kultur Nachrichten* 14 (1973), pp. 37-67.

⁴ Robert Ouvrard, *1809 Les français à Vienne: Chronique d’une Occupation*, Fondation Napoléon, (Paris: Nouveau Monde, 2009), pp. 239–53. [There is also an online version on Ouvrard’s website.](#) To the best of our knowledge, the only Napoleonic history specialist who made use of the Klosterneuburg Abbey Archives is Leighton S. James. See: *Witnessing the Revolutionary and Napoleonic Wars in German Central Europe*, War, Culture and Society, 1750-1850, (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2013), pp. 132–3, 136, 138.

⁵ Stiftsarchiv Klosterneuburg [hereafter StAKI] K 219 Nr. 37 ‘Gregor Hummels Notizen zum Jahr 1809’ [hereafter Hummel *Notizen*], 8 June 1809.

⁶ For more on the style and perspective of the Klosterneuburg authors, see: Ilya Bekovich, Sabine Miesgang and Michael Wenzel, ‘Als österreichische Jäger das Stift Klosterneuburg beschossen: Eine Episode aus dem Kriegsjahr 1809 im Spiegel der Quellen’, *Frühneuzeit Info* 33 (2022), pp. 183–91 [here pp. 184–6].

⁷ StAKI K 219 Nr. 37 Hummel *Notizen*, 3-4 July 1809.

View of the Klosterneuburg Monastery in the early 18th century. Note the two flood islands in the Danube. Source: StAKI, Hs. 27/1, fol. 1v-2r.

battle of Aspern-Essling on 21st and 22nd of May. This was followed by a while doing so⁸. The waving and the shouting were likely intended to alert the Austrian pickets on the other side of the lull in the fighting, but the danger remained that the French would attempt further landings in Floridsdorf or further upstream. To prevent the enemy from establishing additional bridgeheads, the entire Austrian 5th Army Corps under the command of Prince Reuß-Greiz was assigned to guard the Danube between Floridsdorf and Krems and on to Linz. The French-occupied bank was closely watched from designated posts labelled as observatories. The main observatory opposite Vienna was established on Bisamberg under the command

of Captain Schönermark of the Austrian General Staff who submitted daily reports on troop movements and signs of bridge construction on the French side of the river. The Austrians used further ways to obtain intelligence on the enemy. At night, scouts, messengers and spies landed regularly across the Danube. During the day, when crossing the river was impossible, other ways were devised to transmit information quickly. Probably the most imaginative was what might be called the 'Nußdorf laundry telegraph'. By hanging various pieces of laundry in different colours, an informant in the riverside village of Nußdorf was able to communicate to the Austrian posts in *Schwarz-Lacken-Au* the strength and march directions of enemy detachments

moving along the main road between Klosterneuburg and Vienna. These reports were duly entered into the journal of the main Austrian field army. For instance, on July 3rd it was noted that '[at] a certain house in Nußdorf, the confidant had taken out one shirt and some distance away again two shirts and three white ladies bonnets'. The code functioned as follows. The colour of the laundry piece indicated where the troops were going, with blue and red items denoting specific locations to the south; different pieces of white cloth revealed whether the enemy troops were infantry, cavalry or artillery. If a situation arose when the laundry types and colours were insufficient or a more urgent matter was at hand, spontaneous solutions were also devised. On

⁸ Österreichisches Staatsarchiv [hereafter ÖSTA] Kriegsarchiv [hereafter KA] Alte Feldakten [hereafter AFA] 1381 '1809 I (1) Operationsjournale der Hauptarmee und Korps', *Hauptjournal* p. 114 (3 July 1809) and p. 126 (4 July 1809).

the 4th of July, the army journal states that in Nußdorf ‘[the certain person] had waved a white cloth upwards with much joy; it was also clearly noticed how she had ordered two boys to sweep the street upwards with a broom and had always shouted while doing so’.⁹ The waving and the shouting were likely intended to alert the Austrian pickets on the other side of the river that the road to Klosterneuburg was free of enemy troops.

The Austrian posts along the river itself were manned by *Jägers* and soldiers of the *Grenzer* border infantry. Some of these were stationed on the bank itself, while others were placed in advance positions on offshore islands. Communicating with the islands was only possible at night to avoid being detected by the enemy. According to the *Vorpostenkette Total-Ausweiss* [Full Report on the Chain of Foreposts] of General Klebelsberg’s Brigade a typical picket comprised a corporal and three to five men. There were also so-called *Hauptpiquetts* commanded by an *Oberjäger* with 10 or more soldiers.

Intermingled along the line were the Horsemen of the 3rd Ulan Regiment ‘Archduke Charles’ who secured communications and delivered messages. Holding the sector between Korneuburg and the floodplains opposite Höflein, the 4th *Jäger* Battalion under the command of Lieutenant-Colonel Piombazzi maintained a total of 10 regular and two main pickets stationed directly on the river Islands, with a total of 78 soldiers of whom 16 were on duty at any given moment.¹⁰ Directly to the south, with headquarters in the village of Langenzersdorf, the line was held by the 3rd *Jäger* Battalion under the command of Major Daniel Baroni. These were the troops stationed across from Klosterneuburg.

As noted above, by early July Napoleon had ordered the French army to concentrate. Archduke Charles was aware of this development which suggested that the French were likely to attempt another breakout from Lobau island. However, the Austrian command did not follow Napoleon’s example and did not order all its forces to the Marchfeld

to face the French. Concerned about his communications with Bohemia and Hungary, Charles did not summon the two army Corps guarding the Danube line from Preßburg to Linz. Instead, to prevent the French from marching toward Vienna, repeated orders were issued to Austrian units along the river to keep the enemy busy. On July 3rd, reports were received from *Schwarz-Lacken-Au* that many of the Württemberger troops stationed along the Danube north of Vienna had left the previous night. This news prompted Prince Reuß-Greiz to order his Corps to engage the enemy. To this effect, a raid was planned that same night against Greifenstein. The attack was to be carried by five companies of the 8th *Gradiscaner Grenzer*, about 500 men strong, supported by two cannons. In peacetime, that regiment guarded the Habsburg-Ottoman frontier along the Sava River, making its soldiers an ideal choice for an amphibious operation. To confuse the enemy, all Austrian units downstream from Tulln were ordered to act as well.

⁹ Österreichisches Staatsarchiv [hereafter ÖSTA] Kriegsarchiv [hereafter KA] Alte Feldakten [hereafter AFA] 1381 ‘1809 I (1) Operationsjournale der Hauptarmee und Korps’, *Hauptjournal* p. 114 (3 July 1809) and p. 126 (4 July 1809).

¹⁰ ÖSTA KA AFA 1416, ‘1809 V-VII 5. Armee Korps’, VI Nr. 44, *Vorpostenkette von Höflein bis Altenwörth der Brigade Klebelsberg* (9 June 1809).

This included the 3rd *Jäger* Battalion opposite Klosterneuburg, 10 kilometres downstream from where the main attack was to take place.

Lieutenant-Colonel Piombazzi wrote to Major Baroni that: *'I received the order [...] that the enemy should always be alerted if possible. The inactivity along the line of outposts should cease. In particular, the enemy is to be prevented from moving his troops from here down the Danube to reinforce his large army in the Lobau'*¹¹

Piombazzi's order was dispatched from Korneuburg at 7pm, reaching Baroni at Langenzersdorf one hour later. Then it was necessary to wait until dark to convey the order to the foreposts on the islands. Until the regulation of the Danube in the 1870s, a pair of islands lay offshore directly under the Monastery complex. The larger *Uferhaufen* was located closer to the Abbey; the smaller *Uferhaufen* bordered the main stream channel the Danube. Today this area is part of the modern park, *Klosterneuburger Auen*, and the adjacent sports complex. [In July the sun sets shortly after 8pm and the evening twilight takes another one-and-a-half hours.](#)

As demonstrated by these modern re-enactors of the 1st *Jäger* Battalion, Austrian light troops took maximum advantage of the terrain.

Only then could boats leave for *Uferhaufen* carrying the order together with additional reinforcements tasked to distract the enemy garrison inside the Monastery. This fits well with the evidence provided from inside the Abbey that firing began at 11 o'clock at night. This happened as the main Austrian raiding force was boarding the boats opposite

Greifenstein. In that respect, the diversion against Klosterneuburg was perfectly timed. The brightly lit windows of the Abbey offered the only tangible target.

The shooting by the *Jägers* was heavy and continuous, prompting the monks and the Württembergers to vacate the entire wing facing the river. The fact that the Austrians were able to hit the Abbey's windows in the middle of the night from a distance of 200 meters and more, indicates that the troops sent by Baroni against Klosterneuburg were expert marksmen.

Next day, the Württemberger garrison tried to clear the islands from the *Jägers*. This entire incident is recounted by Hermann and Hummel. The Württembergers first bragged pompously, declaring that they would chase the Austrians out of the *Au*. Then they dragged two cannons to the *Uferau*, namely the river bank opposite the islands, and started shooting canister directly toward the Austrians. However, the artillery fire failed to make an impression on the *Jägers*, who first retreated to the eastern part of the island and from there continued to fire back at the enemy's gun crews. Soon, the artillery commander was hit and the Württembergers retreated with their cannons, 'covered with shame' as the Chronicle records with glee.¹² Although neither Herrmann nor Hummel were specialists in military matters, their description makes perfect sense as far as contemporary tactics are concerned. It was enough for the *Jägers* to leave the waterline and hide behind the trees and bushes which covered the rest of the islands. In this situation, firing round shot made no sense as there was no obvious target. The canister – eventually

employed by the Württemberg artillery – was not much better as it was not effective against troops in dispersed formation under cover. Furthermore, canister balls could not penetrate the trees where the *Jägers* had taken position. Even if the two cannons fired quickly and in tandem, this would leave at least half a minute between the canister salvos, allowing sufficient time for individual sharpshooters to break cover and take aimed shots at the enemy gunners. Cannoneers were highly trained soldiers and were not to be squandered in pointless duelling with enemy snipers. The successful silencing of the Württemberg artillery is alluded by Baroni in his operational report written later that evening. Interestingly, the Major omits the fact that his *Jägers* fired directly at Klosterneuburg the night before.¹³ Possibly, Baroni was unsure how well that detail would sit with his military superiors.

As already noted, Major Baroni was aiming to distract the Württembergers from the raid of the 8th *Grenzers* against Greifenstein. The Austrian force was divided into two waves. The first landed successfully shortly before midnight as planned and proceeded to surprise and overrun the Württemberger outpost at Höflein. The second wave was less lucky because the boats lost their way between the shoals. The subsequent report blames the civilian boatmen who '*contributed little to the success of the operation*'. Some boats got stuck and were saved only after two corporals jumped into the water and helped to push them off from the sandbank. As a result, the second landing occurred two hours after the original schedule.

¹¹ ÖSTA KA AFA 1416, '1809 V-VII 5. Armee Korps', VI ad 17, *Obstlt. Piombazy, Korneuburg, abends 7 Uhr an Major Baroni in Langenzersdorf* (3 June 1809).

¹² StAKI K 219 Nr. 37 Hummel *Notizen*, 4 July 1809.

¹³ ÖSTA KA AFA 1416, '1809 V-VII 5. Armee Korps', VI ad 25, *Bericht von Major Baroni, Langenzersdorf* (4 July 1809).

'Two bullets which were shot on July 1809 at 11 o'clock at night by I[mperial]-R[oyal] Austrian Jägers positioned in the Au into the room of the ble[ssed] venerable Ignatius Dauderlau on the second floor of the new building.'

Zwey Kugeln
welche den 3. July 1809.
nach 11 U. bey der Nacht
von den K.K. Loterr., in der nächsten
Au postirten, Jägern in das
Zimmer des sel. Hrn. Venerabilis
Ignatius Dauderlau, im Neugeb.
im 2. Stocke geschossen worden.

By that time, daybreak was approaching and it was further reported that Württemberger reinforcements were marching to Greifenstein. At 6am, the Austrian troops re-embarked with 12 prisoners and returned to their side of the Danube

without suffering any casualties.¹⁴ While the *Grenzers* were operating at Greifenstein, Lieutenant-Colonel Piombazzi moved the 4th *Jäger* Battalion into the nearby floodplains opposite Kritzendorf. Unlike the operational reports of

the 3rd *Jägers* and the 8th *Grenzers*, no detailed account of this action survives. The subsequent entry into the journal of the main field army does not indicate whether Piombazzi's troops made any contact with the enemy.¹⁵ Later on July 4th, three Württemberg regiments arrived at Klosterneuburg. Two of these came from Döbling,¹⁶ which suggest a short-term success in luring at least some enemy troops away from Vienna. However, as with the rest of General Vandamme's 8th Corps, these troops were not earmarked for Napoleon's main thrust from the Lobau.¹⁷ Thus the raid and diversions the night before did not have any influence on the subsequent course of the campaign. This might also explain why the action against Klosterneuburg is missing from all the military histories of 1809. A pair of bullets – presumably fired that night – was preserved by Dauderlau and eventually deposited in the Abbey's archive. Visual examination shows what appear to be groove marks, suggesting these bullets were fired from a rifled barrel. One of the bullets is pressed but not mushroomed, implying a relatively mild impact, with glass window obviously coming to mind. It is hoped that proper ballistic analysis involving measurement and weighing of the bullets could be conducted in the future to establish their provenance and the precise way in which they were fired. Irrespective whether these bullets were indeed shot by Austrian *Jägers* at the night between the 3rd and 4th of July as the accompanying note claims, they prompted the rediscovery of previously unknown military engagements from the War of 1809.

¹⁴ ÖSTA KA AFA 1416, '1809 V-VII 5. Armee Korps', VI ad 24, *Bericht des Major Simbschen des Grenzer Regimentes Gradiskaner Nr. 8* (4 July 1809).

¹⁵ ÖSTA KA AFA 1381 1381 '1809 I (1) Operationsjournale der Hauptarmee und Korps', *Hauptjournal* p. 126 (4 July 1809).

¹⁶ StAKI K 219 Nr. 37 Hummel *Notizen*, 4 July 1809.

¹⁷ John H. Gill, *1809 Thunder on the Danube: Napoleon's Defeat of the Habsburgs*, 3 Vols. (London: Frontline Books, 2008-10). Vol. 3, pp. 197 and 406.